

SYNTHESIS AND PROPERTIES OF NEW OXYGEN-CONTAINING CROWN ETHERS BASED ON DIVALENT ALCOHOLS

Budagova R.N.

Ministry of Science and Education of Azerbaijan Republic, Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry named after Acad. M. Nagiyev, AZ 1143 Baku, 113 G.Javid Aven., Azerbaijan
PhD on Chemistry, Associate Professor, Ministry of Science and Education of Azerbaijan Republic Institute of Catalysis & Inorganic Chemistry named after Acad. M. Nagiyev

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14556858>

Abstract. *The polycondensation reaction of ethylene glycol and trans-cyclohexanediol with ethylene oxide in the presence of alkali has been carried out. Based on the optimum mode of preparation of crown ethers, a new class of organic compounds was selected. Depending on the molar ratio of the initial divalent alcohols and ethylene oxide, new oxygencontaining macrocyclic polyethers were synthesised and investigated. The composition and structure of the crown ethers were proved by ¹H NMR, IR spectroscopy. The physicochemical parameters of the synthesised compounds have been determined. The obtained macrocyclic compounds are promising for their further investigation as extractants of metal ions and catalysts of interfacial transfer.*

Keywords: *crown ethers, polycondensation reaction, ethylene glycol, trans-cyclohexanediol, ethylene oxide, complexing agents.*

Introduction

Macrocyclic compounds are unique chemical compounds that, due to their structural features, have unusual chemical properties, in particular, a high ability to form stable complexes with metal cations [1-9]. The ability of macrocyclic compounds to capture and retain certain ions in a strictly selective manner in accordance with the structure of their intramolecular cavity makes them highly effective specific extractants: they can be used to extract metals from poor ores, gold from solutions, uranium from sea water, and calcium from hard water, as well as to purify wastewater, including atomic production, from harmful impurities. For example, the addition of only a few per cent of 24-crown-8-ether allows the extraction of 99.9 per cent of cesium and strontium. In the same way, radioactive substances or toxic heavy metals can be removed from the body [10-14]. Crown ethers are successfully used in medicine, agrochemistry, fine organic synthesis, analytical chemistry, interfacial catalysis, electrochemistry, metallurgy and other various industrial fields, as well as in the catalysis of redox biochemical processes. In this regard, the research topic related to the improvement of the synthetic approach to crown ethers is relevant.

In the literature there are no data on the synthesis of macrocyclic compounds based on two atomic alcohols [14].

Previously, we developed a method for the preparation of oxygen-containing crown ethers based on alicyclic and aromatic ketones with ethylene oxide [15,16]. Continuing studies in this direction, we have developed and studied a method for the preparation of new oxygen-containing macrocyclic polyethers based on ethylene glycol and trans-cyclohexanediol-1,2 in the presence of an alkali catalyst. The method consists in the interaction of ethylene glycol or trans-cyclohexanediol-1,2 with an excess of ethylene oxide in the amount of 6-18 mol per 1 mol of

initial diols in benzene or dioxane in the presence of catalyser NaOH at a temperature of 45°C and a pressure of 20-30 atm, with a reaction time of 3 hours.

The polycondensation reaction of ethylene oxide with divalent alcohols proceeds according to the following scheme:

Individual crown ethers are obtained through a stage of formation of divalent polyether glycols followed by dehydration of polyether-alcohols to crown ethers.

At excess of ethylene oxide with divalent alcohols with participation of alkaline catalyst the reaction proceeds with the formation of polyalkyl derivatives of different molecular weights and their subsequent cyclisation leads to the formation of various crown compounds.

Experimental part

Control of reaction progress and identification as well as purity of substances were carried out by ¹H NMR-, IR-spectroscopy. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in steady-state mode on a «Bruker-AV 600» instrument with an operating frequency of 600.13 MHz with an internal standard GMDS in DMCO solution. Chemical shifts are given in the scale of δ (m.d.) versus GMDS (0.05 m.d.), J/Hz [17, 18].

During the experiment, IR spectra were recorded on a «Specord IR-80» instrument in a microslice for solid samples using a suspension with vaseline oil [19].

The polycondensation reaction was carried out until cessation of water release, collected in a Dean-Stark trap by means of azeotropic benzene-water mixture. After cooling of the solvent-benzene mixture, the solvent-benzene was removed from the reaction mass at constant pressure on a rotary evaporator.

The residue was acidified with 5 mL of concentrated HCl to an acid reaction (according to the universal indicator).

Then it was washed with water, filtered, further washed with acetone and dried in thermostat. Analytically pure oxygen-containing crown ethers were obtained by recrystallisation from n-heptane. The yields of crown ethers are 86-92% of the theoretical one.

The synthesised crown ethers are viscous oily liquids whose composition and structures were established by NMR ¹H and IR spectroscopy.

IR spectra: the presence of bands in the region 1132, 1135-1138 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of the crown ether fragment, 1440-1500 cm⁻¹ for the polyester chains. 1450, 1354, 1350 (ν_{CH}), 1120 (ν_{CO}) cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR spectra, b.m.s.: 8.2-7.3m.d., 3.56 (s), 4.42 (s), 7.32 (m) m.d., crown ether proton signals appear as multiplets in the region - 4.2 - 2.6 m.d.

Some physicochemical parameters of the obtained macrocyclic polyethers are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Physicochemical parameters of crown ethers of divalent alcohols

Names of the polyethers	T boiling. °C/ 1mm Hg	n _D ²⁰	d ₄ ²⁰	Melting point °C
Cyclohexano-18-crown-6-ether	175-177/1	1.6720	1.1202	30
18-crown-6-ether	133-135/1	1.46950	1.0945	22

The obtained macrocyclic polyethers were used in the extraction-photometric and gravimetric determination of Ni(II) and Pd(II) at pH 3-12.

Conclusions

As a result of a series of experiments, efficient methods for the synthesis of new oxygen-containing crown ethers based on divalent alcohols and ethylene oxide in the presence of an alkaline catalyst have been developed and investigated. The optimum mode of the process for the preparation of oxygen-containing crown ethers, a new class of organic compounds, has been selected. The obtained macrocyclic compounds are promising for their further study as extractants of metal ions and interfacial transfer catalysts.

REFERENCES

1. Citterio D.C., Sasaki S.A., Suzuki K. A New Type of Cation Responsive Chromoionophore with Spectral Sensitivity in the Near-Infrared Spectral Range. *Chemistry Letters*, 2001, 30,(6), 552–553, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1246/cl.2001.552>
2. Gokel G.W., Leevy W.M., Weber M.E. Crown Ethers: Sensors for Ions and Molecular Scaffolds for Materials and Biological Models, *Chem. Rev.* March 2004. 104 (5), 2723–2750. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr020080k>
2. Steed J.W., Atwood J.L. *Supramolecular Chemistry*. John Wiley and Sons. New-York. 2000. (1): 480.
3. Katayama Y., Fukuda R., Iwasaki T., Nita K., Takagi M. Synthesis of chromogenic crown ethers and liquid–liquid extraction of alkaline earth metal ions. *Analytica Chimica Acta Anal. Chim. Acta* 1988, 204, 113-125. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670\(00\)86350-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670(00)86350-3)
4. Ushakov E.N., Alfimov M.V., Gromov S.P. Crown ether-based optical molekular sensors and photocon-trolled ionophores. *Macroheterocycles*. 2010, 3.(4), 189.
5. Gromov S.P., Alfimov M.V. Supramolecular organic photochemistry of crown-ether-containing styryl dyes. *Russ Chem Bull*, April 1997. 46, 611–636. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02495186>
6. Ushakov E.N., Alfimov M.V., Gromov S.P. Design principles of optical molecular sensors and photocontrolled receptors based on crown ethers. *Uspekhi chemii*, 2008, 77(1):39-59.[*Russ.Chem.Rev.(Engl.Transl.)*,008,77(1):39]
7. Gromov S.P., Ushakov E.N., Vedernikov A.I., Lobova N.A., Alfimov M.V., Strelenko Y.A., Whitesell J.K., Fox M.A. A Novel Optical Sensor for Metal Ions Based on Ground-State Intermolecular Charge-Transfer Complexation. 1999, 1, (11):1697–1699. *Org. Letter*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/01990710d>

8. Fegtle F.A., Weber E.E. Chemistry of Guest-Host Complexes. Synthesis, Structures and Applications, Mir, Moscow, 1988, 512. [Vogtle F.A., Weber E.E., Host-guest complex chemistry of macrocycles. Synthesis, Structures, Applications, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1985, 421.]
9. Hiraoka M.A. Crown compounds. M: Mir, 1986, 345.
10. Pedersen C.J. In Nobel Lectures in Chemistry. [Ed. B. Malmstrom] Wold Scientific Publishing Co.Singapore. 1993. 495.
11. Pedersen C.J. Cyclic polyethers and their complexes with metal salts *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1967, 89, 2495-2496. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ja-00986a052>
12. Bogatsky A.V., Lukyanenko N.G., Kirichenko T.I. Crown ethers and cryptands. *Journal of the All-Union Chemical Society named after D.I. Mendeleev*, 1985, 30, (5): 7-19.
13. Yatsemirsky K.B., Kolchinsky A.G., Pavlishchuk V.V, Talanova G.G. Synthesis of macrocyclic compounds, Kiev: Naukova Dumka, 1987, 277.
14. Budagova R.N., Zeynalov S.B., Sadikhova S.K. Epoxy- and crown ethers. Synthesis, properties and application of epoxy and crown ethers. Lap Lambert Akademik Publishing. 2017, 67.
15. Budagova R.N., Zeynalov S.B., Sultanzade S.S., Magerramova L.M. Synthesis spiro-crown-ethers on the basis of ketones and their derivatives. *PPOR Journ.* 2019. 20.(3): 265-272.
16. Gunter H.A. Introduction and course of NMR spectrometry. Moscow. 1984. 92.
17. Aniskov A.A. Determination of structure of carbocyclic compounds by spectral methods. Saratov. Ich. 'Nauka'. 2010. 234.
18. Tarasevich A.A. IR spectra of the main classes of organic compounds. Lomonosov Moscow State University 2012, 55.